

5GinFIRE and the Automotive EVI

Miguel Luís

Instituto de Telecomunicações
Aveiro, Portugal

5GinFIRE.eu

contact@5GinFIRE.eu

[5GinFIRE](https://twitter.com/5GinFIRE)

5GinFIRE

- **Main goal:** to build and operate an Open, and Extensible 5G NFV-based Reference (Open5G-NFV) ecosystem of Experimental Facilities (...) laying down the foundations for instantiating fully softwarised architectures of vertical industries and experimenting with them.
- Driven by architectural (standards) and technological (open source) convergence principle.
- Initial focus on **Automotive** & Smart Cities verticals.

5GinFIRE ecosystem

Automotive EVI inside 5GinFIRE

Automotive EVI inside 5GinFIRE

- N-PMIPv6 vehicular *ad-hoc* network with
 - IEEE 802.11p/WAVE;
 - IEEE 802.11n (Wi-Fi);
 - Small Cell C-RAN 4G supported by OAI;
 - In-car node processor with additional sensors (cameras, positioning, ...).
 - Simultaneous multihoming:
 - more than one technology in use;
 - Mobility support:
 - transparent handovers for the end-user.

Automotive is a hot topic!

- 7 automotive 3rd party experiments within 5GinFIRE
 - Extending VANET capabilities:
 - SURROGATES (University of Murcia, Academia)
 - MIGRATE (OdinS, SME)
 - CV2XinFIRE (FERON technologies, SME)
 - Safety:
 - VRU-Safe (University of Athens, Academia)
 - 5G-CAGE (University of Murcia, Academia)
 - Multimedia/Infotainment:
 - CAVICO (iTTi, SME)
 - 5G-DT (Elios, SME)

SURROGATES

- Main objective:
 - Extend the 5GINFIRE OBUs with a mobile IPv6 communication stack, and then delegate computing and cache tasks of a set of services near the edge, by means of virtualised images of the OBUs.

SURROGATES

- Implementation and VxFs deployed:
 - **vOBU**: this VNF is instantiated several times to cover the virtualization needs of physical OBUs. They are deployed in the OpenStack domain of IT-Av automotive;
 - **OBU manager**: this VNF has been deployed at IT-Av premises too;
 - **Data analytics**: its global nature justifies its deployment in the central 5GINFIRE backend at 5TONIC;
 - **Service**: a general VNF has been created as reference service to collect and show data from vehicles.

SURROGATES

- Results:

SURROGATES

- Results:

RTT delay solving data requests [ms].

RTT delay in request resolution within the 5GINFIRE framework [ms].

CAVICO

- Main objective:
 - to adapt CAVICO context-aware video controller as a VxF for automotive EVI environment offered by IT-Av in 5GINFIRE project and test innovative QoE features of the CAVICO solution while merging QoE and QoS parameters.

CAVICO

- Implementation and VxF deployed:
 - **CAVICO**: is responsible for interpretation of video stream, GPS data and network throughput. Every time, when a new request is received, the control algorithm calculates current FPS, video resolution and stream bit rate using information about the use case, observed video QoE and measured network throughput.

CAVICO

- Results:

Trajectory.

Use case.

FPS.

Bitrate.

Video resolution.

VRU-Safe

- Main objective:
 - Experimental evaluation of a network service with computing and networking capabilities to identify Connected Vehicles and Vulnerable Road Users in potentially dangerous situations based on several contexts (Vehicle & VRU position, movement direction, accelerations, etc.), by predicting their trajectories and forwarding the respective notifications to both sides.

VRU-Safe

- Implementation and VxFs deployed:
 - **Trajectory Computing Component:** processes the acquired contextual information and generates position prediction matrices based on OBUs velocity, direction, etc. The matrices are then forwarded to the HINS VxV.
 - **Hazard Identification and Notification Service:** processes the information and detects any potential collisions.

VRU-Safe

- Results:

OBU A.

OBU B.

5G-CAGE

- Main objective:
 - Deploy and test a City Safety solution using monitoring and analytics of video streams collected from heterogeneous and distributed sources in order to validate a new Public Safety NFV Network Service.

5G-CAGE

- Implementation and VxFs deployed:
 - **CODet**: It will be able to detect via Computer Vision and Machine Learning algorithms (deployed at the edge) specific objects such as car plates and brands.

5G-CAGE

- Results:
 - Processing time

Locally processed.

Processed in the Cloud.

5G-CAGE

- Results:
 - Network load, from the OBU to the RSU.

The Future of IT-Av Automotive EVI

- Becoming a city-scale platform
 - UIA European Project: Aveiro STEAM City
 - IT-Aveiro
 - Altice Labs
 - University of Aveiro
 - Municipality of Aveiro
 - INOVARIA
 - CEDES

- With new functionalities
 - 5G RAN
 - C-V2X
 - Virtualization in the vehicles

Contributors

b com

Odin **S**

ELIOS srl

ΠΑΝΕΠΙΣΤΗΜΙΟ
ΠΑΤΡΩΝ
UNIVERSITY OF PATRAS

ITTI

feron
TECHNOLOGIES

uc3m | Universidad **Carlos III** de Madrid

HELLENIC REPUBLIC
National and Kapodistrian
University of Athens

University of São Paulo
Brazil

5GinFIRE.eu

contact@5GinFIRE.eu

[5GinFIRE](https://twitter.com/5GinFIRE)

5GINFIRE

Thank You!

Miguel Luís
(nmal@av.it.pt)

5GinFIRE.eu

contact@5GinFIRE.eu

[5GinFIRE](https://twitter.com/5GinFIRE)